

Remarks on morbus cardiacus (scorbutic pericarditis) and on paracentesis of the pericardium in the same

[Bemerkungen über den Morbus cardiacus (Pericarditis scorbutica)
und über die Paracentese des Herzbeutels in demselben]

by **Dr. A. Kyber,**

Medical inspector and first senior physician at the Naval Hospital in Kronstadt.

This is a series of 5 papers in: Medicinische Zeitung Russlands (1847) issues 21-25:

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11034121?page=166,167> p.161-165.

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11034121?page=174,175> p.169-172.

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11034121?page=182,183> p.177-181.

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11034121?page=190,191> p.185-190.

<https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11034121?page=198,199> p.193-197.

Translation of the first and last paper to English are in this document.

They were translated to assess the work to which Dr. Spodick referred to, see below.

An English summary of Kyber's work was published in the Ranking's Abstract (1848):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175404>

Kyber's work was cited in:

Spodick DH. Another cardiac disorder in scurvy. N Engl J Med 1970;282:686.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM197003192821215>

Spodick DH. Medical history of the pericardium. The hairy hearts of hoary heroes.

Am J Cardiol. 1970;26(5):447-54.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4920772>

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This annotated version was prepared by:

Harri Hemilä, University of Helsinki, Finland

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä

Indications that scurvy was particularly common in Russia in the 1700-1800s.

There were a number of reports of scurvy in Russia in the 1800s, which are consistent with Kyber reporting that “*We are used to seeing a form of scurvy appearing endemically in Kronstadt every year, especially in spring, either sooner or later, which lasts more or less throughout the summer until late autumn when it goes into hibernation*” and “*we find people suffering from scurvy in the hospital at any time of the year*”.

Hirsch (1885, p.526-567)¹ described the high rate of scurvy in Russia as follows:

“Of the 143 epidemics in the table,² 35 belong to Russia alone, not counting the outbreaks in the Crimean War; and among these there were three, in 1840, 1845, and 1848-9, which extended over a great part of the empire. It follows, accordingly, that **Russia is one of the chief seats of scurvy at the present date, although less so than in former centuries;** the malady is **still endemic in** the Baltic provinces, and in St. Petersburg, where 2680 cases of it have been treated within the last eighteen years in the Obuchow Hospital alone. It is **endemic also in** the governments of Olonetz and of Novgorod (mostly in the circles of Beloserki, Kiriloff, Borovitsch and Tichvin), along the shores of the Arctic Ocean and other parts of the Siberian littoral, such as the Amoor region (10.9 per 1000 of the troops quartered there in 1875-78 having been attacked with scurvy), and in Kamtchatka. We have other accounts of **its endemic prevalence** in Asiatic Russia from the districts on the Chinese frontier, and from Tomsk. Also, for Russia in Europe, from the government of Kasan, but more especially from the southern provinces of the empire—Jekaterinoslav, the Steppes of Saratov, the Ukraine and adjoining districts of Western and Little Russia, and the Crimea. Mention is made also of **endemic** scurvy in Kutais (Transcaucasia). The focus of scurvy in Southern Russia joins on, as Felix tells us, to the endemic of it in the adjoining districts of Roumania.

The part played by scurvy in North-Western Europe is very much less.”

1 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179>
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/526/mode/2up>

2 See Table starting at p.521:
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/520/mode/2up>

Reports on scurvy in Russia:

De Mertans C. Observations on the scurvy. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond* 1778;68:661–680.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16846144>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/106342>

“many gentlemen merchants and strangers were attacked by a slow scurvy, having their gums soft, swollen, and blueish, the breath strong, and many scorbutic spots at the legs, whilst it was rare to find among the lower people, either of town or country, a single person with these marks....” (p.665-666)

Description of scurvy in Vyborg by Nitzsch (1732, 1734)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17295494>

John Cook on scurvy in Russia (1738-1739)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299869>

Description of scurvy in the Russian Army by Nitzsch (1747).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296086>

Lee. An account of scurvy, as it has recently prevailed in some parts of the Russian territory. *Lond Med Phys J.* 1826;55(328):465-468.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5646568>

Seidlitz. On haemorrhagic pericarditis. *Br Foreign Med Rev.* 1836;1(1), 259-263.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175282>

Ravages of scurvy in Russia. *West J Med Surg.* 1852;9(2):172-173.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10436923>

“The symptoms were those usually described: In the severer cases, general weakness, indurations of the muscles, especially those of the inferior extremities, hemorrhages, &c.; as sequelæ, dropsies, dysentery, passive inflammations of internal organs, gangrene, and typhus of a putrid type were observed...

The total number of scorbutic cases amounted to 260,444, of which 67,958, or more than a fourth part, proved fatal.”

Goedecken. On the occurrence of several spontaneous fractures of the ribs in a scorbutic individual. [English Abstract] *Br Foreign Med Rev.* 1838;6(11):220-228.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5590333/?page=8>

Comrie JD. Scurvy in North Russia. *Edinb Med J.* 1920;24(4):207–15.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5294660>

Other evidence that vitamin C depletion causes cardiac disorders.

Effects of scurvy on the heart were described already by James Lind (1772):

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

and by Lewis Rouppe (1772)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227637>

and by Alfred Hess (1920)

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

and there are several reports indicating that vitamin C has effects on the heart, e.g.:

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM1934030821010> Pericardial effusion

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34316783> Pericardial effusion

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37680776> Pericardial effusion

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38504249> Pulmonary hypertension

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31403849> Pulmonary hypertension

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27682441> Right heart failure

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35282368> Left ventricular ejection fraction

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28143406> Atrial fibrillation

Introduction

The interesting forms of scurvy that have been little discussed so far include, indisputably, the *scorbutic transudations of the serous membranes*. In the otherwise assessable monographs on scurvy, as in most textbooks and handbooks on specialised pathology and therapy, we find neither the characteristic pathognomonic signs nor anything specific about the treatment of these forms. We therefore believe that readers will understand when, in these papers, we try to address briefly a specific form of this family of diseases, and in particular report on a course of treatment that, as far as I know, was first carried out in the hospital for which I am personally responsible.

It is the long forgotten heart disease of Caelius Aurelianus,³ which we have been observing every year for more than a decade, and the disease in question was written about identically as such by Seidlitz in his treatise (Hecker's New Annals Vol. 9.),⁴ so that, in order to avoid repetitions in this respect, we too must refer to this classic treatise. In the major hospitals here, particularly in **naval and military hospitals**, this disease is called **scorbutic pericarditis** and exudative sanguineous pericarditis. But since both the symptoms and also the course are significantly different from those of true pericarditis, I prefer the old name **morbus cardiacus** as, to me, the concept of the disease seems to be more comprehensive. In recent years, there have been assessable contributions on these and similar forms: G. v. Samson, currently a full professor in Dorpat, in his "Beobachtungen über den Scorbut" [Observations on scurvy],⁵ Berlin, 1843; also Schönberg, in an essay which can be found translated into Russian in "записки по части врачебныхъ наукъ" [Notes on Medical Sciences], Saint Petersburg, 1844", and W. Von Samson "Über den Scorbut" [On scurvy] in Häser's Archive Vol. V, Chapter 4.

3 HH looked at the texts of Caelius Aurelianus and there did not seem to be any indications that the described cardiac disorders were caused by scurvy.

4 Seidlitz (1836) On Haemorrhagic Pericarditis. [Short abstract of a 60 page report]
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175282>

5 Observations on Scurvy. Br Foreign Med Rev. 1845.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5613527>

With regard to why we did not find a description in the manuals earlier, there may be the following reasons for this:

1) The disease is only seen endemically in coastal regions of the far north, and here too only

2) in a certain class of people who are more exposed to the general influence of scurvy found all year. We found morbus cardiacus almost exclusively in the military, and mainly in the sailors of the military navy. Anyone who has served in the navy will find this easy to explain, as it is precisely the sailors serving in the fleet who are exposed far more to the damaging effects of scurvy in general than the rest of the military. Although we also observed scurvy, among other known forms, in the rest of the working class poor every year, this form of morbus cardiacus was found almost exclusively in sailors.

We are used to seeing a form of scurvy appearing endemically in Kronstadt every year, especially in spring, either sooner or later, which lasts more or less throughout the summer until late autumn when it goes into hibernation. Endemic conditions which, although kept within limits, can never be completely eliminated and social conditions in which the sailor lives here favour scurvy in general on this island,⁶ and even though there are years in which it appears less severely than in others, it is never absent: indeed, due to the meteorological observations carried out in late autumn and winter, mainly concerning the cold, dryness or humidity of the atmosphere and the barometer readings, etc., we are able to make a fairly certain prediction about the scurvy that will arrive in spring.

This endemic form of scurvy now also causes the appearance and greater or lesser severity of the symptoms of morbus cardiacus, as we will discuss further below.

3) It is only since we have learned to recognise the physical signs in recent decades that we have also become certain about the presence of transudation in general. Palpation, percussion, auscultation and mensuration can only allow us to recognise its presence with certainty. How many cases may not have been due to acute hydrothorax, or even apoplexy, in earlier times!

4) From the above, post-mortem examination of the bodies gives us the ultimate irrefutable proof. This can only be carried out almost exclusively in larger hospitals, but can only rarely be carried out in private practice, and it is therefore understandable that with a large number of post-mortems we can bring together more experience and the resulting conclusions.

Before we list the pathognomic signs of this form and before we discuss their nature and the prognosis, we will therefore present post-mortem findings, then the reader will be better able to recognise the symptoms and assess the means I have suggested.

⁶ Kronstadt.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kronstadt>

Post-mortem findings

Often we find nothing notable on the outer surface of the body. We often see a strong, well-fed, robust body lying before us without any external signs of scorbutic diathesis. More often, however, we find the characteristic signs of scurvy, even if not to a high degree, but, nevertheless, the visible manifestations of this disease. These include ecchymotic patches, spots on the lower limbs, as well as the livid colour of the body. After removal of the sternum, we now constantly find the pericardium to be a bluish taut sac, without any other change in the fibrous membrane and the cellular tissue covering it. In some cases (especially in the chronic form, as will be discussed in the pathognomy below), we have found the fibrous membrane thickened, the cellular tissue rich in fat, and clump-like accumulated gelatinous, yellowish infiltrations in places.

Depending on the greater or lesser quantity of transudate, the expansion of the pericardial sac is significant, often one foot or more in length and diameter. If you now split the pericardium you encounter a thin, more or less dark red to blackish opaque fluid, the quantity of which usually varies between 3 to 8 pounds.⁷ There was only one case where we found the enormous quantity of 10 pounds.

This fluid consists mainly of a protein-containing serum, with fibrin mixed in with it, in which we believe we have seen red blood cells under microscopic examination. But they seemed to us more elongated, often angular in shape, and the edge of these cells was not as well-defined as the blood cells of healthy blood compared to this transudation. The microscopic investigations have only recently been carried out by us, very fleetingly, and still leave much to be desired. If this apparently blood-like fluid is left in a vessel, the reddish substance separates out, albeit slowly, but over time sinks to the bottom and forms a greasy mass which does not coagulate, and a slightly reddish clear liquid remains above it.

On its surface the inner layer of the pericardium exhibits layers of a cinnamon-red-coloured exudate, some thicker and some thinner, which project freely into the surface with net-like elevations and depressions. This firmer precipitate is either in the form of a simple more or less easily torn coating, usually only loosely adhering to the serosa, or it is divided into several layers which can be separated from each other, of which the layers closer to the serosa are always firmer and less red in colour, and sometimes form a complete membrane themselves. The precipitations projecting into the pericardial cavity sometimes appeared to be exactly like a blood clot, being of the same consistency and colour as one. If the transudate fluid was absorbed in whole or in part during life, or removed as a result of surgery, the pseudomembranes appeared to be more fibrous, whiter and caused greater or lesser fusion of the heart with the pericardium. If you remove the precipitates, the pericardial serous membrane is either not reddened at all, at most slightly bluer than usual, or there are traces of an apparent inflammation of the serous membrane, with infiltration, and even vascular development.

In some rare cases, a reddish, extensive, blotchy redness is found; in others, and this is usually the case, the red is more bluish, with dark spots, streaky, but with clearly visible vascular branches. In others, there are actual bruises of dark red, bluish, or even blackish colour, without any underlying more marked vascular development being visible.

⁷ 1 Pound = 0.45 kg.

The serous membrane that covers the heart itself behaves somewhat differently. Either this too exhibits those reticulated reddish deposits on its surface, only in far thinner layers; or (as is usually the case) it has a ragged appearance formed by small bright red or yellow spots and warts, an appearance which is also found, albeit less frequently, on the inner surface of the pericardium. In other cases, these warts lengthen into flaps, scraps that hang freely into the cavity; or the surface of the heart looks very much like a honeycomb. If you remove these villi, under the barely altered serous membrane of the heart you find an unusually thick layer of fat up to one inch thick, a phenomenon that occurs in most cases. The heart itself is smaller, compressed, the musculature is pale, shrivelled, easily torn, as though the heart had been cooked, macerated, as it were. The endocardium is either unchanged or a livid red. The chambers of the heart contain mostly large, sometimes even fairly firmly adhering polypous clots.

The transudate in the pericardium now occurs either on its own in morbus cardiacus, or at the same time there is a very similar transudate in the chest, and even in the abdominal cavity. We have quite often had cases where ascites, which was not complicated by heart disease, made paracentesis of the abdomen necessary and what appeared to be a very similar fluid was drained.

The left lung is always pushed backwards, drained of blood, almost membrane-like, which can easily be explained by the pressure exerted by the filled, taut pericardium; the right lung, on the other hand, is overfilled with blood. In addition, all the signs of previous or concomitant pneumonia or pleurisy may now be present.

In the other organs, apart from the general changes caused by scurvy-related dyscrasia, only a few changes specific to this disease were present. The liver is always pushed down, usually slightly softened. In the peritoneal cavity you always find a greater or lesser amount of exudate from the serum.

Finally, we ask the question: *Is the fluid in the pericardium, which constitutes the characteristic part of the post-mortem examination, blood or not?* Is it just a coloured, serous exudate? And then a result of acute inflammation of the pericardium? There are many things to consider here; and even if, for reasons soon to be given here, we prefer to agree with the opinion that it is transudate blood from the serous membrane of the pericardium, there is still a need for some evidence that we cannot yet provide, as we still need to learn lessons on this from chemical and continued observations under the microscope.

The following reasons led us to assume that this fluid is blood: its external appearance is almost identical to the venous blood. The blood cells were clearly visible under the microscope. The only missing sign was the lack of coagulability of the blood, and the lack of fibrins. Only if we assume that the transudate, that has appeared suddenly and has been present in the pericardial cavity for a longer or shorter period of time, is kept in continuous motion due to the constant, rhythmic beats of the heart, then the fibrous material or fibrins may well have been secreted, precipitated so to speak, and those coatings on the serous membrane and the heart itself, those layers and villi created due to an anomalous type of development, are the result of these fibrins being absent from this transudation.

Most likely cause

We will now examine, as briefly as possible, the nature or most likely cause of the morbus cardiacus. At the same time, we ask the interested reader to bear in mind that we are not inclined to deliver a scholarly work, which we lack the time to do in our onerous, overburdened business. We are primarily only concerned here, after a concise report of what we have seen, to report on the healing process, which has provided us with surprising phenomena and results.

We believe the most likely cause to be in the effusion of a bloody transudate from the capillary vessels of the serous membrane into the pericardial sac, which either occurs suddenly, without previous pathological phenomena, similar to apoplexy, or which we saw developing as a result of previous pathological symptoms caused by a paralytic state of the capillary vessels of the serous membrane of the pericardium (if we may assume one), in the case of prevailing general scorbutic diathesis, where there is slackening of the elasticity and reduced contractility of the muscle fibres. It is also caused by the times of year favouring scurvy, which soon change into rheumatic, rheumatic-catarthal or even rheumatic-gastric conditions and therefore mainly explain more clearly the effect on the serous membranes and here those of the thoracic viscera, under the known side effects.

We constantly see that the onset of morbus cardiacus, or so-called exudative sanguineous pericarditis, is linked to certain times of year, and specifically to the time when we see scurvy appearing endemically on our island, i.e. from early spring to the beginning of autumn. Although we find people suffering from scurvy in the hospital at any time of the year, we have found over a number of years that it always occurs endemically during the period mentioned above and can then occur together with almost all diseases. And it is precisely when this endemic status demands our attention the most, that we observe the onset of morbus cardiacus. We saw the earliest cases towards the end of January, only once in nine years; they usually start appearing in February.

The intensity of the endemic is in exact proportion to the fact that the number of people suffering from it usually becomes most significant in the month of April, decreases gradually in summer, and fades out in autumn. But, as has already been mentioned above, there are also years when we observed morbus cardiacus more rarely, and indeed in those years in which the scurvy was milder. So, in 1839 and 1840 scurvy appeared at its most severe, an observation that was also made in several places, even many hundreds of miles away from here. In 1840 only 40 cases of death from morbus cardiacus were seen on post-mortem examination; the following years were characterised by the occurrence of milder cases of scurvy, and in the same proportion the incidence of morbus cardiacus was lower, so that on average the number of people who died from this disease was not greater than 12. In 1845 the appearance of scurvy, and this form of it, was more favourable but the number of people who died from the same disease was far from that of 1840.

We must also add that morbus cardiacus occurred most noticeably at the time when the rheumatic-inflammatory nature of the disease was most prevalent in the hospital. The more marked the thoracic viscera were seen to become inflamed, which is usually the case in April and May, the more frequently were cases of morbus cardiacus seen too, which also gave rise to the same being regarded as true inflammation of the pericardium with its

consequences, whereas, however, the course of the symptoms of the disease, and the unreliability, indeed even the harmfulness of the anti-inflammatory process, are sufficient.

If the character of the disease at a time of year is more catarrhal-rheumatic in nature, as we also saw the disease manifest itself, then we believe that we were more successful in the treatment of it. Also the symptoms proved to be less severe; we also noted that strong young men succumbed more to this disease. Most suffering from the disease were between 25 and 42 years of age, on the other hand, younger people rarely succumbed to the disease. Men were most likely to suffer from morbus cardiacus and we did not encounter a single case of a woman succumbing to it, but then the female sex is far less likely to contract scurvy at all: at least we observed severe scurvy in naval and military staff and the poor working classes, fewer or no forms of scurvy in the women of these classes, although there were sufficient causes for it to be present, which we cannot discuss here due to lack of space.

Nationality had a decisive influence on this disease, as on scurvy in general. While we see Russians with their tougher fibres less predisposed to scurvy, we find it more prevalent among the inhabitants of the Baltic Sea provinces, in particular among the Estonians and Latvians, and it can be assumed that $\frac{3}{4}$ of the victims are from these provinces, while only $\frac{1}{4}$ of them are Russians. The looser fibres of the Estonians and Latvians actually predispose them far more to scurvy. Nor should we overlook the temperament which, among other predisposing factors, has a decisive influence on the production of scurvy. And it is precisely here that we find that the Russian is generally more happy and cheerful than the Latvian and Estonian, who is self-contained, more inclined to gloom, and therefore succumbs to nostalgia, to this great factor producing scurvy mainly in the military, more than in any other nationality.

(To be continued.)

(Conclusion)

3) Johann Saal, from Livland,⁸ a strong young man with a good constitution, a sailor of the 18th fleet, was admitted to this naval hospital on 31st July 1845 with chest pain. The patient's medical history showed that he was suffering from severe pleurisy and had had to undergo venesection twice. On the third day the stitch he suffered in his left side had disappeared and only a cough remained. On the 7th day his temperature had gone down due to sweating; on the 8th day a dull pain was felt again around the heart, his limbs were trembling, he had cold blue lips and the tip of his nose was cold and dyspnoea had started; the pulse was suppressed. On 9th August in the evening at 5 pm the patient was transferred to the Department for chronic diseases under the Medical Officer Isaak. His condition was as follows: he complained of tightness of the chest, but more about an indescribable anxiety, and general overheating of the skin, although both feet and hands felt ice-cold; he also complained of severe pain in the lower limbs,⁹ the severity of which was the same day and night: scorbutic spots were also seen on his lower limbs.¹⁰ His face had a livid, bloated appearance¹¹ and his eyes looked lifeless; his lips were cold and livid as was the tip of his nose. On the neck there was marked distension of the jugular veins. The patient complained of dizziness and light-headedness, which tended to occur particularly when standing up, therefore he also preferred to lie in a horizontal position, with a tendency towards the left side, with his head very low being his favourite position. Towards evening coughing started but it was not severe and it was productive. The tightness of the chest and anxiety were sometimes so severe that the patient tossed back and forth and he changed his position for a short time but the position described above was his preferred position. He had no appetite at all, his tongue was clean but very pale; stools were normal; his lower abdomen was not painful anywhere on applying deep pressure; the liver area was greatly enlarged; he only passed a little urine; the pulse could hardly be felt. His chest measured as follows:

Top right 17¾"	top left 17¼"
Bottom right 18¾"	bottom left 17.4".

Below the right half of the chest extended by ¾", above by ¼", on the left, however, it extended by rather more than ½". Percussion of the chest produced a good tone to the lungs, but the area around the heart produced a muffled, dull sound on percussion to a significantly greater extent than would be expected from a heart of normal size. Breathing sounds were good overall, the heart sounds on the other hand were weak and sounded distant. We considered this case to be one of morbus cardiacus and decided, in order to save the patient's life, to perform paracentesis of the pericardium, which was then carried out at around 6 pm in the evening by the assistant to the senior physician, Hofrath Lang, at the usual site between the 4th and 5th rib using a trocar of Schuh, as a result of which

8 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Livonia>

9 Pains are typical of scurvy.

10 Spots are typical of scurvy. When there are several cases of scurvy, it is reasonable to conclude from the red spots that a patient suffers from scurvy.

11 Swelling of lower limbs, but also of face is common in scurvy.

around 1½ pounds of dark blood was emptied and, although percussion indicated that there was still fluid present in the pericardium, no more could be removed because the heart appeared to be lying in front of it.

A short time after the procedure, the pulse was raised but was very weak; the anxiety had decreased significantly and the patient was able to tolerate lying on his right side.

2½ hours after the procedure his condition was as follows: the feeling of anxiety had disappeared completely; the patient breathed fairly freely; his dizziness and light-headedness had disappeared; the lips had lost their livid appearance, had become warmer, only the tip of the nose remained cool and the eyes still had a lifeless appearance. The jugular veins were still slightly distended; the pulse had improved and was 70 beats per minute; the feet felt cold although the patient complained of an unpleasant burning sensation in the skin of the chest, of the back and of the thighs. Systole of the heart could be heard closer and had even become clearer, at times it was as though a splashing sound could be heard. He was prescribed an arnica infusion with dilute hydrochloric acid, and also a blister plaster was placed on his chest.

10th August. The patient felt better, but his sleep was restless and he had a few attacks of uneasiness and anxiety, but these soon passed and appeared to be spasmodic in nature. The livid bloated appearance of the face had disappeared. His lips and nose felt warm, with their normal colour returning. His gums were spongy and bled easily¹² – the odour from his mouth was disgusting, – the tongue was clean, but very pale. He had absolutely no appetite, whereas his thirst had increased, and he wanted acidic drinks. His cough was insignificant, his breathing easier than yesterday and deep breathing was far easier than before the operation. The patient only felt pain at the wound from the surgery, but to a small extent. The tightness around his heart had reduced significantly and he was able to empty his bowels in the morning, he passed little urine, his pulse was better but not entirely even, but it was no longer intermittent. On breathing in deeply the breathing sounds could be heard clearly all over the lungs and coarse crackles were only heard in the area of the upper margin of the shoulder blade. Systole of the heart was shorter and clearer, and therefore also far easier to hear than before the operation. Instead of the arnica, 15 grains of chininum sulphuricum were administered every two hours.

11th August. The patient's condition was not so satisfactory. He was very restless, the tightness in the area of his heart and significant dyspnoea had started. Every position in which he lay was uncomfortable, therefore he was continually tossing and turning. His breathing was more difficult and breathing in was only possible with effort. His cough was insignificant. His face exhibited anxiety, his lips and tip of the nose were livid and cool again, his mouth was almost always open, the tongue was rather coated at the root. He was able to pass motions but little urine and it was dark-coloured; the pulse was uneven, sometimes interrupted; the activity of the heart was very irregular at times, so that on placing a hand on the area of the heart a recoil sensation could be felt. The breathing sounds on breathing in deeply were normal all over and only in the left lung were there some crackles. The heartbeat was heard as being very close, at times stronger and at times weaker and sometimes interrupted. Systole was accompanied by a bellows-like sound, which could not always be heard, however. To reduce the increased heart activity, the quinine was stopped and nitrum was given in an Althea decoction.

¹² Swelling and bleeding of gums is typical of scurvy, as well as a disgusting smell of breath.

[12th]? August. Our patient's condition worsened and the symptoms of the disease were more marked. The patient complained of a dull headache and the feeling of tightness and pressure in the chest remained unchanged; his pulse occasionally did not correspond to the activity of the heart, as the heartbeats could be heard strongly and clearly with small, suppressed pulses. Consequently, a disturbance in the small circulation occurred and venesection was carried out to resolve it; after the removal of 5 ounces of blood, the pulse rate increased, the anxiety and dyspnoea decreased but with 10 ounces removed the pulse rate dropped again and the patient felt faint, therefore the blood vessel was closed. Around 3 hours later the patient's condition was as follows: the anxiety and the tightness in the area of the heart had abated somewhat, breathing was easier than it had been, the lips etc. were warm again, the tip of the nose cool, the mouth was closed and his headache had disappeared completely, his pulse was raised though weak at 72 beats per minute. On laying a hand on his heart the recoil sensations could no longer be felt. Both heart sounds could be heard rather closely with the stethoscope. Systole was occasionally also accompanied by a weak bellows-like sound.

13th August. The patient complained of serious weakness although he had slept peacefully for a few hours in the night. The tightness in his chest had decreased; his breathing was easier; his lips were warm but livid; his tongue was coated at the root. He passed a motion in the morning, his pulse was faint and uneven. Instead of nitrum an arnica flower infusion with potassium acetate was prescribed.

14th August. The patient's weakness had increased in general; the other symptoms were as they were yesterday. He was given wine and his body was washed down with aromatic vinegar twice a day.

15th August. The patient breathed more easily but during the night he had isolated attacks of anxiety and tightness of the chest. His lips and tip of his nose were livid, his eyes were dull; his tongue was fairly clean but pale; **the gums were spongier**; stools normal; little urine was secreted and it was dark and cloudy, cough insignificant; the pulse was uninterrupted but weak at 75 beats per minute. The sound in the area of the heart was still rather dull. Instead of the earlier medicine, hydrochloric acid was used and lemon juice was given to drink.

16th, 17th and 18th August. There was no change. The blister plaster on the chest was replaced. In the evening of the 18th, the patient's condition had deteriorated again: he complained of shivering and of a feeling of heat in his skin. His breathing was not very constricted but he had a very bothersome cough with expectoration. On breathing deeply, however, there was absolutely no pain but there was on external palpation of the left half of his thorax. The pulse had accelerated and was clear at 182 beats; the arnica and acid had to be stopped again and salmiak with Althea decoction was prescribed to be taken internally.

19th August. The breathing difficulties were not severe but the cough was very bothersome but with less expectoration. The patient was able to raise his head higher but he complained of **great weakness and pain in his thighs**, shivering followed by a sensation of heat in his dry skin and persistence of the **scorbutic ecchymoses on the lower limbs**. His eyes had more life, his pulse more energy and was regular at 85 beats per minute. Percussion in the area of the heart produced a fairly good sound; the heart sounds came

from closer to the chest wall and were stronger; normal breathing sounds could be heard from the right lung but there were loud crackles in the left lung. The medication was continued.

20th August. The patient was sweating a little on his back and he had slept peacefully for a few hours; in the morning there was less coughing than yesterday; the expectoration had become more copious and the pulse rate had decreased by 5 beats per minute.

21st August. He had started to sweat again to some extent in the night; there was less coughing and the expectoration was thick, sticky and clear. He had not started shivering again; the pain in his limbs had become less bothersome but the dry heat was still present to a lesser extent; dyspnoea was insignificant; the percussion sound in the area of the heart was good and the heart sounds could be heard clearly. The medicine was suspended and the patient was prescribed a warm bath.

Until 30th August his condition remained almost unchanged, but it was noticeable that he had a tendency towards oedema, which now developed gradually. Initially his feet were swollen, then ascites followed. It took rather a long time for this to be removed; the cough too worried us, which finally only abated with the use of salmiak in combination with senega root. The more the oedema developed, the less the dyspnoea became, and nothing else abnormal was seen in the pericardium or in the chest since that time. Although convalescence progressed very slowly, he did, nevertheless, recover with fortifying and diuretic agents. The patient displayed a great desire for wine and over one week he was given 2 ounces of port wine three times a day with 5 drops of catharidum tincture. Ph. castr.

On 1st October the patient looked healthier; his strength increased; the scurvy had disappeared, so that he was able to leave his bed at this time; but it was not until 15th October, until all the symptoms of disease, including the signs of scurvy and the oedema, had pretty much disappeared; only towards the middle of November were we able to discharge the patient as being fully recovered. Since then he has remained healthy and I am able to see him daily as he works in the hospital as a medical orderly.

Concluding remarks.

Since we are now concluding this treatise with these three medical histories, to which we could add a large number of similar ones, we need not fear overstepping the limits set for us in allowing ourselves to make the following brief remarks. We believe that with these medical histories we have shown how intensively sulphuric acid quinine proved to be effective. In the *first* case we saw immediately after it was used that large doses of this agent greatly increased activity in the vascular system: this was proven in particular by the constant temperature fluctuations in the evening and the dryness of the mouth. In the *second* case we also saw a clear increase in the pulse rate, pressure in the epigastrium and even vomiting. In the *third* case due to the use of large doses of quinine the activity of the heart increased to hyperaemia so that venesection had to be performed. However, it appeared to us that these pathological symptoms were necessary conditions for starting the healing process, for increasing the reaction of the central organ of the blood circulation to produce the great momentum required to produce an artificially created inflammatory

process, which brought about adhesion of the pericardium with the heart, in my opinion the only way in which to achieve recovery from this disease.

Case No. 1 gives us a clear picture of the first acute form of morbus cardiacus in its pure form. If we exclude the rough dry skin and the livid colour of the face, we found **absolutely no external signs of scurvy being present:**¹³ indeed over the months in which he was consigned to bed, there were no clear signs in this subject of scurvy developing, which are, however, so commonly seen in other patients who, without having scurvy, are forced to keep to their beds due to their respective illnesses, and are kept in hospital: cases that cannot be avoided, in spite of all the care given and attention to keeping the air clean around the patient and giving him a nourishing diet.

The other two cases exhibited more the second chronic form suggested by us, in which scorbutic dyscrasia was already predominant even before morbus cardiacus started to play its main role. Also we do not want to deny that it may appear to some of our readers that the doses of quinine¹⁴ are too large, we can only say that I and a number of my superiors can testify that even in those cases which had an unfortunate outcome, those large doses were tolerated for several days, indeed for a whole week without us seeing particularly dramatic reactions.

We still consider it our duty to state that our treatment methods in the hospital in these as well as in all other cases were completely transparent and made public. Freely and boldly and certain of my diagnosis, the operation was carried out several times in the presence of well-known foreign doctors, performed by myself and a number of my superiors. In 1844, when the personal physician of the King of Prussia, Dr. Grimm, together with the Prussian doctor Dr. Weise, visited the hospital entrusted to me, and precisely found a case of morbus cardiacus in the hospital, I assigned the operation to staff doctor Schönberg. In 1846 I did the same in the presence of Division Doctor Dr. Spilleffsky Exc. As the visit by these gentlemen lasted only a short time, they were only able to convince themselves of the safety of the operation itself, and the immediate surprisingly beneficial effect on the sick individual.

As I am unaware that the operation for morbus cardiacus has been carried out anywhere else, I believe that I can claim priority with full rights from the medical world that the Kronstadt naval hospital is the first to do so.

However, there needs to be improvement of and tailoring of the therapeutic procedure after the operation because, although we believe that we are on the right track, we do, however, need to determine more closely the size and combination of the doses of quinine. In the next few cases I intend to give this together with phosphoric acid and phosphorus and will publish successes with this later. If we regard phosphorus as the most invigorating and stimulating of our medicines, that is used in all paralysis-related conditions, I believe that in combination with sulphuric acid quinine, which works specifically on the contractility of the fibres, we must expect a great deal from phosphorus, as the nature of morbus cardiacus can, however, only be found in the paralysis-like state of the capillary vessel system of the pericardium and the heart with secondary transudation.

13 There is no basis to propose that the cardiac disorder in a patient is caused by scurvy when “absolutely no external signs of scurvy being present”.

14 Quinine is not a drug for scurvy.

In any case, Johan Saal had a number of symptoms consistent with scurvy, see above.